

**Report on the definition of wind atlas output parameters:
Catalogue of output parameters to be stored in the data
base and output parameters of the model chain
Deliverable D4.1 – Final version**

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Executive Summary

This report summarizes in the first three sections the procedure that has been followed within the first twelve months of the NEWA project in order to outline the final product of the project, a New European Wind Atlas data base.

For this, potential future users of the New European Wind Atlas were invited to take part in a questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a new wind atlas data base for Europe. It turned out that the stakeholders were especially interested in long-term time series data from meso-scale simulations (the length of the period covered by the wind atlas expected by the stakeholders is about 25 years, the temporal resolution expected by the stakeholders is about 10 minutes and the spatial resolution expected by the stakeholders is about 1 km) as well as in a well-documented methodology that allows for a further downscaling of the meso-scale time series to a target site with a micro-scale model. Moreover, the participants of the questionnaire were especially interested in information on extreme values and on detailed guidelines how the data provided in the wind atlas data base can actually be used. On the other hand, there was interest but at a slightly lower level also in additional statistical data. The stakeholder expectations were summarized to a preliminary list of NEWA output parameters.

In a second step, the results of the questionnaire were presented for discussion within the consortium in order to adapt the full amount of stakeholders' expectations to a technically feasible amount taking into account the limited real and computing time that will be available to derive the wind atlas data base and the limited disk space that will be available to host the data base. This step included presentations on several workshops of the project as well as a second, but this time project internal survey.

The resulting, preliminary suggestions for the contents of the New European Wind Atlas are documented in detail in this report. They were presented for a final discussion at the NEWA WP 3 workshop in Barcelona in September 2016, being the basis for the final list of suggested NEWA output parameters and the conclusion of Task 4.1 of the project.

Introduction

The main objectives of task 4.1 of the NEWA project were to include the interests of potential future users in the development of the New European Wind Atlas and to harmonize the expectations of the stakeholders with the currently available possibilities of models, computing resources and storage.

Consequently, the work in task 4.1 was divided into two major steps. Results from both steps are provided in detail in this document.

In step 1 the stakeholders were invited to communicate their expectations to the NEWA consortium by taking part in an online questionnaire and during a common workshop with members from the IEC topical expert group on “Assessment of wind resource, energy yield and site suitability - Input conditions for wind power plants” (IEC 61400-15) which took place on October 2nd, 2015 in Paris. The online questionnaire that has been distributed to potential users of the New European Wind Atlas is presented in chapter 1, while the answers obtained from the participants of the questionnaire are summarized in chapter 2.

Based on the results of the questionnaire a first suggestion for the contents of the New European Wind Atlas has been derived. This suggestion, which is presented in chapter 3, was discussed in the second major step of task 4.1 with the members of the NEWA project. The discussion took place with a couple of project partners during the NEWA workshop on “Nordic Experiment” that took place on February 2nd and 3rd, 2016 in Copenhagen. Moreover, in order to obtain feedback from further project members the presentation that had been shown in Copenhagen was also distributed via the NEWA mailing lists of the three work packages 2, 3 and 4 of NEWA to all project partners. A further presentation was held during the project meeting in Perdigao in May 2016. As a result from the presentation there a second survey was organized in which the project participants could evaluate the suggestions for the list of output parameters. The objective of the project internal consultations was to adapt the list of wishes derived from the results of the stakeholder analysis to a specification of the New European Wind Atlas that is actually technically feasible. The results of the project internal evaluation of the list of output parameters can be found in chapter 4. These results were again presented to the project participants during a workshop in Barcelona in September 2016. The final specifications for the New European Wind Atlas after the final discussion in Barcelona are presented in chapter 5.

Some specifications need still to be finalized, but this will be done at a later stage of the project when the required results from related tasks are available. The additional specifications will then be documented in deliverables related to these tasks.

1. Questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas

In order to guarantee that the product that will be developed in the framework of the NEWA project, the New European Wind Atlas, meets the needs of the stakeholders, it was planned to involve the stakeholders directly in the process of outlining the contents of the New European Wind Atlas at the time, when the proposal was written.

Following the example of the Global Wind Atlas [Hallett et al., 2013] it was decided to collect the expectations of the stakeholders to a new wind atlas data base for Europe by asking them to participate in an online questionnaire. Although the results obtained from the analysis of the answers given to the questionnaire concerning the expectations towards a Global Wind Atlas have been published only about three years ago, it was nevertheless thought that a new questionnaire concerning a New European Wind Atlas would still make sense. The Global Wind Atlas should especially assist the development of renewable energies in developing countries. The focus concerning the development of public authorities and project developers in these countries might be different from that of these groups in Europe.

The questionnaire concerning the stakeholders' expectations on a new European Wind Atlas was hosted by ThesisTools.de, which runs a website on which surveys can be published free of charge. The link to the NEWA questionnaire was <http://www.thesisools.de/web/survey/507152>.

The full questionnaire consisted out of 33 questions. The analysis of the answers obtained showed that participants who answered to all questions in the questionnaire required about 30-45 minutes to finalize the questionnaire. The number of questions to which the participants were asked to answer was partly dependent on the answers given by the participants. The participants were also allowed to skip certain questions. It was possible to fill out the questionnaire anonymously, but the participants had also the possibility to leave their contact details. Those participants who communicated their contact details will be informed on the results of the questionnaire and the suggestions for the New European Wind Atlas derived from them. They will continuously be updated on new developments in the NEWA project.

The link to the questionnaire was distributed via a mailing list on which e-mail-addresses were collected that are available from different wind energy associations (e.g. EWEA and Bundesverband WindEnergie) and it was sent to the project partners together with the request to distribute it among potentially interested contacts. Moreover, the link to the questionnaire was published in a newsletter of the EWEA. The period in which the questionnaire was online was extended several times in order to allow more people to take part in the questionnaire and finally the period in which the questionnaire was online was from October 8th, 2015 to March 10th, 2016.

In the following, the questions of the questionnaire will be presented supplemented by some background information concerning each specific question, i.e. it will be explained why each specific question was asked and what its importance for the later derivation of a suggestion of the output parameters of a New European Wind Atlas was.

The questionnaire started with a welcome page on which some background information concerning the NEWA project and the role of the questionnaire within it were provided to the participants. This included the rough outline of the New European Wind Atlas that has been provided in the NEWA proposal. For more detailed background information and information on the latest developments within the project the users were referred to the web page of the NEWA project that can be accessed under the link <http://www.neweuropeanwindatlas.eu>.

Question 1:

With this question the participants were asked whether they would like to fill out the questionnaire anonymously or whether they were willing to provide their contact details. The main reason for collecting the contact details of the participants was to be able to discuss the suggestion for the contents of the New European Wind Atlas derived based on the answers given to the questionnaire with a group of stakeholders. Moreover, allowing the participants to leave their contact details enabled us to contact participants in case that any unclear answers were given to questions in the questionnaire.

Question 2:

In case that the participant decided to leave his or her contact details, he or she was asked for his or her name, the name of his or her organization, the name of his or her country and his or her e-mail address. The initial idea behind asking for the country of the participant was to check whether the participants were well distributed among Europe and to check whether there are special needs in special countries. E.g. project developers in Spain with its complex topography could have different expectations to the New European Wind Atlas compared to project developers in the Netherlands.

Question 3:

All participants were asked to select among pre-specified types of organizations those ones which fit best to the type of their organization. The pre-specified types of organization were: consultancy, project developer, university, research institute, non-governmental organization, public authority, investment company, power company, grid operator, wind turbine manufacturer. In case that none of the pre-specified organization types fitted to the participant's organization, it was also possible to explicitly specify an additional organization type. The initial idea behind the introduction of this question was to allow for a later weighting of the answers of the participants. E.g., in case that the expectations of researchers and project developers concerning the New European Wind Atlas were significantly different from each other and it seemed to be impossible to fulfill the expectations of both groups, the expectations of the project developers should get the higher weight.

Question 4:

With this question the participants were asked to describe their personal field of work. This question was introduced in order to check whether the participant would indeed be a potential user of the New European Wind Atlas. This should allow to give answers of obvious non-users of the New European Wind Atlas a lower weight.

Question 5:

Here, the participants were asked whether they have experience with using data from existing wind atlas data bases. In case that they answered the question with yes, the users were asked to answer a couple of additional questions (questions 6 to 9). An additional reason for the question was that people who are already using data from wind atlas data bases might also be more likely users of the New European Wind Atlas. Therefore, it might make sense to give their answers a higher weight compared to those of other participants.

Question 6:

The objective behind this question was to find out for which purposes data from wind atlas data bases are typically used. The purposes for which it is made will evidently have an impact on the contents of a wind atlas data base. E.g. regional wind resource estimates might have clearly different expectations to wind data than grid integration studies. Pre-given answers were: regional wind resource estimates, wind resource estimates for specific sites, input for energy yield predictions for wind farms, wind turbine design for specific environments, site specific assessment of wind turbine power predictability, grid integration studies, regional planning, balancing studies. Moreover, there was an empty field in which the participants could specify any other purpose for which they are currently using data from wind atlas data bases.

Question 7:

Here, the participants were asked to specify the wind atlas data bases they are currently using. The New European Wind Atlas should provide at least the data that the participants are used to get from the wind atlas data bases which they are currently using.

Question 8:

Here, the participants could specify which information they are missing in the wind atlas data bases they are currently using. It should be the objective to include this information in the New European Wind Atlas.

Question 9:

Here, the participants could specify the advantages of the wind atlas data bases they are currently using compared to other wind atlas data bases. The New European Wind Atlas should combine the advantages of different already existing wind atlas data bases.

Question 10:

Here, before asking another question it was explained that the proposal of the NEWA project considered time series data from downscaling of reanalysis data with a meso-scale model as the backbone of the New European Wind Atlas. All participants were asked whether they could imagine to utilize these time series. If they answered no, no additional questions concerning the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas would be asked to the participant. However, in case that they answered yes or despite answering no explicitly chose to answer questions on the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas, a couple of additional questions were asked to the participants. The answers to these questions given by people who intend to use the meso-scale part of the wind atlas could actually be given a higher priority.

Question 11:

According to the proposal of the NEWA project, the final meso-scale wind atlas will cover at least a time period of ten years and the spatial resolution of the meso-scale wind atlas will be at least 3 km. Moreover, it was intended to achieve a temporal resolution of at least ten minutes. In question 11 the participants of the questionnaire were asked whether they would prefer a higher temporal resolution, a higher spatial resolution or an extension of the length of the meso-scale wind atlas in case that the available computational and storage resources allow for an improvement compared to the specifications given in the proposal. Therefore, the objective of this question was to achieve a utilization of the available resources in full agreement with the needs of the stakeholders.

Question 12:

Here, it was mentioned that one objective of the NEWA project is that the data from the meso-scale wind atlas can be used to run micro-scale models for detailed site assessment calculations. In case that the participant is already using a micro-scale model for site assessment calculations, he or she was asked to describe the data that the meso-scale wind atlas would at least have to provide in order that the participant can run his or her micro-scale model. Therefore, this question should serve two objectives. The first aim was to increase the acceptance of the New European Wind Atlas by the stakeholders by enabling them to run their standard tools with data from the meso-scale wind atlas. The second aim was to get an overview over already existing meso- to micro-scale coupling procedures as a starting point for the development of a new coupling methodology in the framework of the NEWA project that should become the new standard of coupling methodologies.

Question 13:

By this question the participants who are interested in using the meso-scale data to run their standard micro-scale model were asked to specify which micro-scale model they are actually using. Again, the objective of this question was to guarantee that data from the meso-scale wind atlas can be applied as driving data for standard tools currently used by the stakeholders. This might increase the acceptance of the New European Wind Atlas.

Question 14:

Here, we presented a list of possible output parameters for each grid point of the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas. However, as the storage is limited, it might not be possible to provide all specified parameters in the final product of the New European Wind Atlas. Therefore, we asked the participants whether they were of the opinion that a parameter specified on the list of possible output parameters was absolutely required, nice to have or not required at all. As a lesson-learned from the questionnaire concerning the Global Wind Atlas, we provided only these three categories to the participants. In the questionnaire for the Global Wind Atlas there were five categories. Two of the categories were “very important” and “important”. In the end most of the parameters were specified as either “very important” or “important” by all participants. In our questionnaire it was explained to the participants that “absolutely required” has the meaning that data for the parameter is absolutely required in order to enable the participant to do his or her current work. The category “Nice to have” was explained as that the participant can do his or her current work without having data for this parameter but that he or she would most probably use data from this parameter in future when it would become available, as the participant saw potential to improve the results of his or her work by using data for this parameter. Finally, the meaning of the category “Not required at all” was that the participant does not need data for this parameter – neither for his or her current nor for his or her future work. The list of parameters specified consisted out of statistical as well time-series parameters. The parameters were mainly collected during two workshops that took place during the NEWA project meetings in March and June 2015. In detail the list contained the following parameters: mean wind velocity, mean wind power density, mean air density, mean turbulence intensity, mean shear parameter, wind speed distribution, wind speed distribution per wind direction sector, characteristics of the diurnal cycle, characteristics of the annual cycle, variance of mean wind speed, probability distribution of the stability parameter inverse Obukhov length, time series of wind speed, time series of wind direction, time series of turbulence intensity, time series of air density, time series of air temperature, time series of humidity, time series of planetary boundary-layer height, time series of inverse Obukhov length, time series of roughness length, underlying elevation data, underlying land use data.

Question 15:

Here, the participants were given to add other parameters that had not been specified in the list of parameters under question 14 but which they consider to be important to be included in the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas.

Question 16:

By this question the participants were asked to specify those five parameters that they consider to be the most important parameters to be included in the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas. In addition to the specifications made in the answers to questions 14 and 15, this question should help to identify the parameters that have really to be included in the New European Wind Atlas.

Question 17:

Also the objective of this question was to get the opinion of the stakeholders what should be done with extra computational and storage resources available to the project. Here, it was asked whether additional resources should be invested into an increase of the spatial resolution of the meso-scale part, specified as at least 3 km in the NEWA proposal, or of the micro-scale part, specified as at least 30 m in the NEWA proposal.

Question 18:

Here, we explained that due to the limitation of the available storage also the number of vertical levels of the wind atlas will be limited. Therefore, we asked the participants to specify those ten vertical levels that they considered to be absolutely required to be included in the New European Wind Atlas.

Question 19:

According to the proposal of the NEWA project, the micro-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas will provide statistical data with a spatial resolution of at least 30 m. In question 19 the participants were asked to specify in which kind of statistics they were actually interested, i.e. which kind of statistics they require to do their work. Five types of statistical data were pre-defined in a list and the participants were asked whether in their opinion a type of statistical data was “absolutely required”, “nice to have” or “not required at all”. The meanings of the terms “absolutely required”, “nice to have” and “not required at all” were defined in the same way as under question 14. The pre-defined types of statistical data were “Annual statistics”, “Monthly statistics”, “Daily statistics”, “Hourly statistics” and “Hourly statistics in dependency on the season”. The meaning of “Annual statistics” was that statistics were derived on the basis of data from the whole time period of the wind atlas. “Monthly statistics” meant that separate statistics are calculated for each month of the year (but note that this includes still averaging over data from several years), while “daily statistics” meant that separate statistics are calculated for each day of the year (again note that this includes averaging over data from several years). Finally, the meaning of “hourly statistics” was that separate statistics are derived for every hour of the day (again averages over several years would be calculated), but on the basis of data from the whole year, while for “hourly statistics in dependency on the season” the basis would only be data from a specific season of the year (again mean values over several years would be determined).

Question 20:

Here, the participants were asked to specify for which parameters statistical data should be provided in the micro-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas.

Question 21:

In the proposal of the NEWA project it was stated that the vision for the level of accuracy of the data provided in the New European Wind Atlas is 3%. It turned out i.a. during the meeting with the IEC topical expert group on wind resource assessment in October 2015 that this objective is very ambitious. E.g., even the long-term accuracy of wind speed measurements at meteorological stations fulfilling the standards of the World

Meteorological Organization (WMO) is not better than 5%, while the short-term accuracy might be 2%. Thus, it is unclear whether it could actually be proven that an accuracy of 3% were achieved for the wind speed data provided in the New European Wind Atlas. Therefore, in question 21 the participants who might be aware of the lacking accuracy of measurements were asked what level of accuracy of the data in the New European Wind Atlas would still be acceptable for them. The answers by the participants could lead to an adjustment concerning the objectives for the level of accuracy required to make the NEWA data base of interest to the stakeholders.

Question 22:

Here, the participants were asked what kind of uncertainty information would be useful for them. Would it be useful to know how much for each grid point the mean values of the parameters provided in the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas change when the setup (e.g. the settings for the planetary boundary layer scheme) of the meso-scale model used for the downscaling is changed, i.e. if an ensemble approach for the dynamical downscaling is applied. Or would it be more useful to provide uncertainty information that specifies how much e.g. the mean wind speed at specific sites within a grid box of the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas deviates from the mean value for the whole grid box. If they had other visions for uncertainty information that should be provided, the participants could also communicate their ideas. As the resources in the NEWA project are limited, it might be necessary to focus on a certain uncertainty estimation approach. Therefore, it was the objective to be able to prioritize a certain approach on the basis of the stakeholder's requests specified as answers to question 22.

Question 23:

In the NEWA proposal it has been mentioned that approaches should be developed with which an information on the predictability of wind resources on different time scales from short-term (day-ahead) to long-term (decadal) in dependency on the kind of terrain and climate zone could be delivered. In question 23, the participants were asked whether they were actually interested in corresponding data and if so, whether they were interested in getting information on the long-term or the short-term predictability of wind resources. Again this question was asked with the objective to define the work that will be done in the NEWA project in a finer detail taking the interests of the stakeholders into account.

Question 24:

Here, the participants were asked whether information on icing and if so, which information exactly, should be provided in the New European Wind Atlas. The objective of the question was to see whether information on icing events would increase the value of the New European Wind Atlas to such an amount that huge resources should be spent on deriving corresponding information which is not a standard output of a meso-scale model but requires some postprocessing of the meso-scale data.

Question 25:

This question dealt with extreme events. The participants were asked whether they were of the opinion that for each grid point information on the “extreme wind speed”, the “extreme gradient of wind speed in time”, the “extreme wind shear” and the “extreme turbulence intensity” was absolutely relevant, nice to have or not relevant at all.

Question 26:

Here, the participants were asked on the recurrence period for which the corresponding extreme values should be specified. Moreover, they were asked for which other extreme events in addition to those specified under question 25 information should be contained in the New European Wind Atlas.

Question 27:

Here, the participants were asked whether also information on wave parameters should be provided for the offshore regions that will be covered by the New European Wind Atlas. If the participants answered to this question with yes they were asked to specify which wave parameters exactly would be required. The objective of these questions was to see whether some work should be spent on the derivation of wave parameters in the NEWA project. Again such information cannot directly be derived from the downscaling approach using a meso-scale model. One option would be to couple a meso-scale model with an ocean model which would require a considerable amount of resources.

Question 28:

The topic of question 28 was the kind of access to the data of the New European Wind Atlas which the participants would prefer. The participants could choose between the options “Online maps”, “Downloadable data files”, “Software” and “Direct access to data base”. Moreover, the participants could suggest other kinds of access to the data. A well-accepted kind of access to the data of the New European Wind Atlas might be a key parameter to increase the acceptance of the New European Wind Atlas among the stakeholders.

Question 29:

In addition to question 28 it was asked in question 29 which kinds of access the users would actually use. The pre-specified kinds of access were the same as under question 28.

Question 30:

In question 30 the participants were asked in which data format the data of the New European Wind Atlas should be delivered. Pre-specified data formats were “NetCDF”, “CSV”, “GIS data” (in addition the participants were asked to specify which GIS data format they would prefer if their favourite data format was a GIS format) and “Direct access to data base”.

Question 31:

As the NEWA project is a publicly funded project the data of the New European Wind Atlas will be made publicly available without costs. Nevertheless the stakeholders were asked to estimate the value the New European Wind Atlas would actually have for them if it were provided in a form which would agree with their expectations. The participants were asked to specify an amount for an annual payment. The objective of this question was to justify the investment into the NEWA project. Moreover, the question can be considered as a preliminary market analysis in case that after the NEWA project e.g. the area that is covered by the New European Wind Atlas will be extended without public funding.

Question 32:

In question 32 it was explained at first that the area that will be covered by the New European Wind Atlas contains the EU countries plus 100 km offshore. Then, it was asked which additional areas would be of interest for the stakeholders. Again, this question is part of a market analysis for e.g. a non-public funded extension of the New European Wind Atlas.

Question 33:

Question 33 offered the participants to finally summarize their basic requests and expectations to a New European Wind Atlas. The objective was to collect additional input for the New European Wind Atlas that could not be obtained from the answers to the previous 32 questions in the questionnaire.

2. Results of the questionnaire

In this chapter the answers given by the participants to the questionnaire on stakeholder's expectations to a New European Wind Atlas will be presented.

Altogether 88 accesses to the questionnaire have been recorded. But only in 26 cases the amount of questions answered was large enough in order to include the questionnaire in the analysis of the results.

Question 1:

Among the 26 participants whose answers were taken into account in the analysis of the results of the questionnaire, only 9 people preferred to fill out the questionnaire anonymously (see Figure 1). On the other hand 17 people agreed to provide personal information.

Figure 1: Answers provided by the participants to question 1 of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas. By this question the participants were asked whether they would like to fill out the questionnaire anonymously or whether they agree to provide their contact details.

Question 2:

All 17 participants who agreed not to fill out the questionnaire anonymously did actually provide information on their names, the names of their organizations, their countries and their e-mail addresses. Due to the protection of data privacy the list of contact details obtained is not included in this document

About half of the participants who agreed to provide personal information came from Germany (see Figure 2). The second largest group of known participants came from Spain, where the questionnaire has actively been promoted by one of the project partners in his personal network.

Figure 2: Analysis of the countries of origin of those participants who agreed to provide personal information in the online questionnaire on stakeholders’ expectations to a New European Wind Atlas.

The high percentage of participants coming from either Germany or Spain could mean that the answers given in the questionnaire are not representative for the whole of Europe. Thus, one has to be careful when the results of the questionnaire are interpreted.

Question 3:

With about 1/3 of all participants in the questionnaire the share of people coming from research institutes or universities is relatively large (see Figure 3). The main target group who should later benefit from the New European Wind Atlas should be people from knowledge-based services and industry, if the New European Wind Atlas should help to further develop the utilization of wind resources in Europe. In order to check whether the high percentage of people from research institutes or universities leads to biased results, the results for the whole group were always compared with that for a subgroup to which only people from consultancies and project developers belonged. However, no significant differences between these two groups could be found in their answers to a huge share of the questions in the questionnaire.

Figure 3: Answers provided by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders’ expectations to a New European Wind Atlas on question 3 which asked to what kind of organization the participant belongs. To select multiple of the pre-specified answers was possible.

Question 4:

The participants in the questionnaire described their field of work as follows:

- Consultants in the field of yield assessments for renewable energies (11 participants):
 - “Energy yield assessments”,
 - “Responsible for all site assessment related activities worldwide within my organization”,
 - “Renewable energy consultant”,
 - “Energy yield assessment expert”,
 - “Site assessment and wind analysis”,
 - “Site assessment section manager. In charge of site assessment methodology tools and procedures all over the world”,
 - “Consultant in wind resource assessment, training in wind resource assessment, industrial research in wind resource assessment”,
 - “Consultant engineer”,
 - “Meteorological consultant, producer of wind atlases”,
 - “Wind measurements, energy yield analysis, site assessment”,
 - “Micrositing international”,
- Other kinds of consultants (2 participants):
 - “Senior scientist, climate and environment consultancy”,
 - “Research administration, political consultancy”,
- People working in the field of wind power simulation (2 participants):
 - “Development for wind power simulation”,
 - “Wind power meteorology”,
- Researchers (5 participants):
 - “Research in micrometeorology, boundary layer, mesoscale numerical weather prediction”,
 - “Area of applied research and modelling. I work with numerical weather prediction in data assimilation”,
 - “Scientific assessment of meteorological conditions for wind energy generation”,
 - “Research in wind resources”,
 - “Worked for many years as consultant; now scientific employee”,
- Project developer (1 participant):
 - “Plan and build sites for wind energy”,
- Other (2 participants):
 - “Meteorologist”,
 - “Manager regulatory affairs”.

Question 5:

Astonishingly, only about 2/3 of all participants have gained experience in the utilization of existing wind atlas data bases so far (see Figure 4). Even among the people from

consultancies and project developers the percentage of experienced users of wind atlas data bases was not larger.

Figure 4: Answers given by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas to question 4 which asked whether the participant has already collected experiences with wind atlas data bases before.

Question 6:

According to the answers given by participants in the questionnaire the main areas of application of data from wind atlas data bases are the determination of regional wind resources, the determination of the wind resources at a specific site and the utilization of the data as input for energy yield calculations for new wind farms (see Figure 5). Among the participants there was nobody who was using data from wind atlas data bases for the specification of design conditions for wind turbines. There might be two reasons for this. The first reason might be that there were only few people from wind turbine manufacturers taking part in the questionnaire. The second reason might be that existing wind atlas data bases provide not the information that is actually required for the design of a wind turbine such as information on extreme events.

Figure 5: Answers given by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas to question 6 which asked for the purposes for which those participants who have already gained some experience with wind atlas data bases actually use the data of wind atlas data bases. The percentages do not sum up to 100%, as it was possible to select several of the pre-specified answers.

Question 7:

According to the answers given to the questionnaire the European Wind Atlas is still the standard wind atlas used by the participants (see Figure 6). About 90 % of those people who have experiences with the utilization of wind atlases have used the European Wind Atlas. New commercial products such as the Anemos Wind Atlas or 3TIER Wind Data seem still to have a relatively low distribution among the participants. One probable reason might be the costs for these products. One conclusion might be that a free access to the New European Wind Atlas might be a key factor for the promotion of this new data base.

About 1/3 of the participants used also wind data from other sources that had not been specified in the list of wind atlas data bases under question 7. The other sources mentioned by the participants were: Wind Atlas Balkan, COSMO-DE, COSMO-EU, ERA-Interim, Wind measurements, Winddaten für Windenergienutzer (mentioned two times), Vortex Wind Maps.

Figure 6: Answers given by those participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas who have already some experience with existing wind atlas data bases to question 7 of the questionnaire which asked to specify which wind atlas data bases have been used by the participant before. The percentages do not sum up to 100% due to the fact that the participants could select several of the pre-specified answers.

Question 8:

According to the answers provided by the participants they are missing the following information or functionalities in the wind atlas data bases that are currently available to them:

- "Time series without a delay in time compared to observations",
- "Data with a temporal resolution of 1 hour or even 10 minutes",
- "Validated wind profile data providing also information on the diurnal cycle of the wind profile",
- "Data with a very high" (unfortunately not further specified) "spatial resolution",

- “Information on additional parameters such as temperature, humidity, pressure, air density, etc.”,
- “Data in GIS format for easy mapping”,
- “Possibility to easily extract numbers”,
- “Information on the wind conditions offshore”,
- “Information on turbulence intensity”,
- “Possibility to import the data from the wind atlas to Google Earth or GIS tools”,
- “Information on vertical wind profile, turbulence intensity, temperature and extreme events”,
- “Accurate data in complex terrain”,
- “Information about the data sources. Information about long term corrections and about uncertainties and their sources”,
- “Data with a higher spatial resolution that takes into account orography”,
- “Data that is compatible with the WMO standards. Long-term wind data with high temporal and spatial resolution”,
- “Information on uncertainties”,
- “Long-term reference data (such as COSMO data). Higher resolution of the data. Higher accuracy of the data”,
- “Information on the uncertainty of the data. Information on the influence of e.g. buildings and vegetation on a measurement”

Summarizing the answers given by the participants in the questionnaire stakeholders seem to have the following needs concerning an improvement of wind atlas data bases:

- Time series data with a temporal resolution of (if possible) 10 minutes and extending over a long period of time
- Better spatial resolution of the data especially in complex terrain
- Information on uncertainties
- Information on the vertical wind profile
- Data of additional parameters such as temperature, humidity, pressure etc.
- A data base from which number can easily be extracted but which allows also an easy mapping of the data
- Information on extreme events
- Information on offshore conditions

Question 9:

The following items were mentioned as advantages of the wind atlas data bases currently used by the participants in the questionnaire:

- “Easy to work with”,
- “The resolution”,
- “A good local coverage of all areas”,
- “Best agreement with measurements”,
- “30 years of data”,

- “Time series of data”,
- “No statistical information like Weibull parameters, this is technology of the 70s”,
- “Consistent and verified data”,
- “Free availability of the data for use in public authorities”,
- “A better spatial resolution of the data, more realistic wind directions”,
- “Information on offshore wind conditions”

The preliminary conclusion for the conceptual design of the New European Wind Atlas is that it should provide long-term time series of data with a high spatial resolution and it should include offshore regions. Evidently, there are certain wind atlas data bases that provide data from a time period covering 30 years. In this context the vision of a meso-scale atlas covering at least 10 years presented in the NEWA proposal does not sound very ambitious. According to the answers given by the participants it will be beneficial that one methodology will be used to derive a wind atlas for a huge part of Europe. The stakeholders will acknowledge efforts for a verification of the data.

Question 10:

The huge majority of participants (23 of 26) in the questionnaire said that they can imagine becoming a user of the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas. 2 of the participants answered that they will most probably not become a user of the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas, but were nevertheless willing to answer additional questions helping to outline that part of the wind atlas. Only one of the participants was not interested in becoming a user of the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas and refused to answer additional questions on that part of the wind atlas.

Question 11:

The question how potentially available additional computational and storage resources should be re-invested concerning the characteristics of the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas did not lead to a clear result. Slightly less than 50% of the participants answered that the spatial resolution of the meso-scale data should be increased to more than 3 km, while slightly more than 40% answered that the length of the period covered by the wind atlas should become longer than 20 years (see Figure 7). However, to increase the temporal resolution of the data to more than 10 minutes was not considered to be a very urgent task.

Figure 7: Answers provided by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas to question 11 which asked how excess computational and storage resources should be used provided that there are still free resources after the specifications for the spatial and temporal resolution as well as the temporal extension of the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas mentioned in the NEWA proposal have been met.

Asked for the expected length of the period covered by the New European Wind Atlas about half of the participants would be satisfied with a period covering 25 years (see Figure 8).

Figure 8: Answers provided by those participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas who answering to question 11 argued for an extension of the time period that is covered by the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas.

The expectations among the stakeholders concerning the spatial resolution of the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas are clearly in the range of 1 km (see Figure 9).

Figure 9: Answers provided by those participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas who answering to question 11 argued for an increase of the spatial resolution of the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas.

Among those participants who answered that they would like to see the temporal resolution of the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas being increased in fact only one person suggested an increase of the temporal resolution compared to the specifications in the NEWA proposal. This person suggested to provide data with a temporal resolution of 60 s.

Question 12:

The question concerning the data that is required to allow for a downscaling of meso-scale information to the micro-scale gave a wide variety of answers. Many participants mentioned that they consider the development and documentation of such a downscaling approach as the most important part of the New European Wind Atlas. However, they mentioned quite deviating needs for the meso-scale data that would actually be required to do the downscaling. Therefore, there is obviously a need to provide a recipe how to use data from meso-scale simulations for a further downscaling to the micro-scale that is accepted by the majority of people in the community. Several participants wrote that they wish that the downscaling methodology to be developed in the framework of the NEWA project will actually allow generating time series with the micro-scale model. There was less interest in a pre-calculated statistical micro-scale wind atlas.

Question 13:

The following “micro-scale models” are currently used by the stakeholders according to their specifications:

- WAsP (mentioned six times)
- Meteodyn WT
- Zephytools
- Alya
- COBEL
- Calmet
- EMD ConWx

- Vortex
- WRF (mentioned two times, evidently this refers to the LES option available in WRF)

None of the participants in the questionnaire did actually specify that he or she is using OpenFOAM. Therefore, in case that the downscaling methodology from the meso- to the micro-scale to be developed in the framework of the NEWA project will make use of OpenFOAM (as originally proposed), it might need additional efforts to promote the downscaling methodology among the stakeholders.

Question 14:

On the following pages the results of the evaluation of the importance of different pre-specified parameters to be included for each grid point of the meso-scale grid in the New European Wind Atlas by the participants of the questionnaire will be presented.

The first pre-specified parameter was the mean wind speed. Here, mean wind speed means the wind speed averaged over the whole period covered by the New European Wind Atlas. A huge majority of participants considered this parameter as absolutely required for their work.

Figure 10: Evaluation of the importance of the parameter mean wind speed to be included for each grid point in the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas. The numbers provide the information how many percent of the participants selected one of the four pre-defined categories of answers.

Figure 10 shows the results concerning the importance to provide information on the parameter mean wind speed when the answers of all participants were taken into account. If only the answers of those participants who belong to the group of consultants and project developers are considered, the result is not drastically changed. The corresponding percentages obtained in that case are 69%, 15%, 8% and 8% (for the answers absolutely required, nice to have, not required at all and no answer, respectively).

The second pre-specified parameter was the mean wind power density. Again, also here mean means that an average over the whole period covered by the New European Wind Atlas is calculated. The importance of this parameter seems to be considerably lower than that of the mean wind speed before. Less than half of the participants consider this parameter to be absolutely required (see Figure 11).

Figure 11: Evaluation of the importance of the parameter mean wind power density to be included for each grid point in the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas. The numbers provide the information how many percent of the participants selected one of the four pre-defined categories of answers.

Again, there is no dramatically different result when only the answers given by participants belonging to the group of consultants and project developers are analyzed. The corresponding percentages are then 31%, 46%, 15% and 8%.

The third pre-specified parameter was the mean air density, i.e. the air density at a certain grid point of the domain of the meso-scale model averaged over the whole period that is covered by the New European Wind Atlas. A little bit astonishingly the evaluated importance of this parameter is even lower than that of the mean wind power density. Only about 1/3 of the participants consider the mean air density as a parameter which they absolutely require in order to be able to do their work (see Figure 12).

Figure 12: Evaluation of the importance of the parameter mean air density to be included for each grid point in the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas. The numbers provide the information how many percent of the participants selected one of the four pre-defined categories of answers.

In case that only the answers given by members of the group of consultants and project developers are analyzed the result is very similar. The corresponding percentages are then 31%, 46%, 15% and 8%.

The fourth pre-specified parameter is the mean turbulence intensity. According to the answers given half of the participants in the questionnaire consider this parameter to be absolutely required for their work (see Figure 13).

Figure 13: Evaluation of the importance of the parameter mean turbulence intensity to be included for each grid point in the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas. The numbers provide the information how many percent of the participants selected one of the four pre-defined categories of answers.

Again, a very similar result is obtained for the group of consultants and project developers. For this group the corresponding numbers are 46%, 23%, 15% and 8%.

The fifth pre-specified parameter was the mean power law exponent. 58% of all participants in the questionnaire ticked the box indicating that this parameter is absolutely required (see Figure 14).

Figure 14: Evaluation of the importance of the parameter mean power law exponent to be included for each grid point in the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas. The numbers provide the information how many percent of the participants selected one of the four pre-defined categories of answers.

Again the percentages obtained for the group of consultants and project developers were very similar to the percentages obtained for the whole group: 54%, 15%, 15% and 15%.

The sixth parameter offered to the participants in the questionnaire was the wind speed distribution which provides information how often in the period covered by the New European Wind Atlas the wind speed is within in a certain range of values. Such information is absolutely required by about 2/3 of the participants in the questionnaire (see Figure 15).

Figure 15: Evaluation of the importance to include for each grid point information on the distribution of wind speeds in the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas. The numbers provide the information how many percent of the participants selected one of the four pre-defined categories of answers.

In the group of consultants and project developers the corresponding percentages were 62%, 8%, 15% and 15%.

The seventh pre-specified parameter was the wind speed distribution per wind direction sector. Although the wind direction is a key parameter for the strength of wake effects within a wind farm and therefore for the energy yield of a wind farm, a relatively low number of only slightly more than 40% of all participants expressed that information on the wind speed distribution per wind direction sector is absolutely required for their work (see Figure 16).

Figure 16: Evaluation of the importance to include for each grid point information on the distribution of wind speeds per wind direction sector in the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas. The numbers provide the information how many percent of the participants selected one of the four pre-defined categories of answers.

In the group of consultants and project developers the share of participants rating the wind speed distribution per wind direction sector as absolutely required was slightly higher. In detail the percentages obtained for this subgroup of all participants were 46%, 31%, 8% and 15%.

The eighth kind of information that was offered to the participants of the questionnaire was information on the characteristics of the diurnal cycle of the parameters contained in the New European Wind Atlas. In fact to provide such type of information would mean that

mean values of several parameters such as the wind speed would be provided for every hour of the day. Among the participants such type of information is evidently more seen as a nice to have than something that is of fundamental importance for their work (see Figure 17).

Figure 17: Evaluation of the importance to include for each grid point information on the diurnal cycle of certain parameters in the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas. The numbers provide the information how many percent of the participants selected one of the four pre-defined categories of answers.

In the group of consultants and project developers very similar numbers of 15%, 46%, 23% and 15% were obtained.

The ninth type of information that was presented to the stakeholders taking part in the questionnaire was information on the characteristics of the annual cycle of the parameters contained in the New European Wind Atlas. In fact to provide such type of information would mean that mean values of several parameters such as the wind speed would be provided for every month of the year. The interest in such a type of information was only slightly higher than in that concerning the diurnal cycle of parameters (see Figure 18).

Figure 18: Evaluation of the importance to include for each grid point information on the annual cycle of certain parameters in the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas. The numbers provide the information how many percent of the participants selected one of the four pre-defined categories of answers.

In the group of consultants and project developers the interest in this kind of information was evidently smaller. The percentages obtained for the four different possible answers were 15%, 54%, 15% and 15%.

The tenth pre-specified parameter to be evaluated by the participants of the questionnaire was the variance of the mean wind speed. This parameter provides information on the variability of the wind resources at a certain location. In case of two grid points with the same mean wind speed, the grid point where the (grid box) mean wind speed shows the lower variability with time might be the more attractive one. This parameter was also seen more as a nice to have than something that is absolutely required by most of the stakeholders (see Figure 19).

Figure 19: Evaluation of the importance to include for each grid point information on the variance of the (spatially) averaged 10-min wind speeds in the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas. The numbers provide the information how many percent of the participants selected one of the four pre-defined categories of answers.

In the group of consultants and project developers the corresponding percentages obtained for the four different possible answers were 31%, 46%, 8% and 15%.

The eleventh offered kind of information was the distribution of the stability parameter inverse Obukhov length. Evidently, to include information on the atmospheric stability conditions at a certain location is beyond the current state-of-the-art of wind resource assessment. Only 12% of all participants answered that they do absolutely require this type of information for their work (see Figure 20).

Figure 20: Evaluation of the importance to include for each grid point information on the distribution of the stability parameter inverse Obukhov length in the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas by the participants of the

online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas. The numbers provide the information how many percent of the participants selected one of the four pre-defined categories of answers.

Among the consultants and project developers the share of people who said that they require this information was even lower with only 8%. The percentages for the three remaining categories of answers for that group were 69%, 8% and 15%. On the other hand to provide information on the atmospheric stability in the New European Wind Atlas was considered to be absolutely required by more than one quarter of the participants coming from research institutes and universities.

Besides purely statistical parameters also time series information was offered to the participants of the questionnaire. The first parameter for which time series were offered was the wind speed. Generally, the interest in time series data of a specific parameter was higher than in statistical data for the same parameter. Only slightly less than 90% of all participants answered that they do absolutely require time series data of wind speed to be able to do their work (see Figure 21).

Figure 21: Evaluation of the importance to include time series of wind speed in the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas. The numbers provide the information how many percent of the participants selected one of the four pre-defined categories of answers.

Among the members of the group of consultants and project developers the corresponding numbers were 92%, 0%, 0% and 8%.

For the whole group of participants the same results as for the time series of wind speed were obtained for the time series of wind direction (see Figure 22).

Figure 22: Evaluation of the importance to include time series of wind direction in the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas. The numbers provide the information how many percent of the participants selected one of the four pre-defined categories of answers.

For the subgroup consisting of consultants and project developers exactly the same result was obtained for the evaluation of the importance of time series of wind direction as for the evaluation of the importance of time series of wind speed: 92%, 0%, 0% and 8%.

The third parameter for which time series data was offered to the participants of the questionnaire was the turbulence intensity. For this parameter, still half of the participants answered that they do absolutely require time series data (see Figure 23).

Figure 23: Evaluation of the importance to include for each grid point time series of turbulence intensity in the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas. The numbers provide the information how many percent of the participants selected one of the four pre-defined categories of answers.

For the group of consultants and project developers the following percentages were obtained for the four possible answers: 46%, 38%, 0% and 15%. Thus, the evaluation of this subgroup is in good agreement with that of the total group.

Although information on the air density is required to calculate the power produced by a wind turbine, astonishingly, only 23% of the participants answered that they do absolutely require this parameter for their work (see Figure 24).

Figure 24: Evaluation of the importance to include for each grid point information time series of air density in the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas. The numbers provide the information how many percent of the participants selected one of the four pre-defined categories of answers.

For the group of consultants and project developers the following percentages were obtained for the four possible answers: 31%, 46%, 8% and 15%.

Astonishingly, the share of participants that were very much interested in time series data of air temperature was considerably higher than the share of participants that were very much interested in time series data of air density (69% compared to 23%) (see Figure 25 and Figure 24, respectively). In addition to time series data of temperature it might make sense to provide also time series data of pressure so that a time series of density can be derived by postprocessing of these two time series. Unfortunately, time series of pressure were not an item on the list of possible information to be included in the New European Wind Atlas pre-specified in the questionnaire. Thus, no result from an evaluation of the importance of these time series by the participants is available.

Figure 25: Evaluation of the importance to include for each grid point time series of air temperature in the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas. The numbers provide the information how many percent of the participants selected one of the four pre-defined categories of answers.

For the four different possible answers the following percentages were obtained, when only the answers from people in the group of consultants and project developers were taken into account: 69%, 19%, 0% and 12%.

According to the answers given by the participants of the questionnaire the interest in time series data of humidity is only moderate compared with the interest in time series data of wind speed, wind direction and temperature. Only 27% of all participants answered that they do absolutely require time series data of humidity (see Figure 26).

Figure 26: Evaluation of the importance to include time series of relative humidity in the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas. The numbers provide the information how many percent of the participants selected one of the four pre-defined categories of answers.

Among the participants from the group of consultants and project developers the interest in time series data of humidity was only slightly higher. 31% of this group answered that they do absolutely require time series data of humidity, while 54 % answered that such a time series would be a nice to have. None of the participants answered that such data is completely useless and 15% of the participants from this group did not give any answer.

A very low percentage of participants who absolutely required information on that parameter were obtained for the time series of planetary boundary-layer height. Only 12% said that they do absolutely require the data. On the other hand 15% answered that they do not require the data at all (see Figure 27).

Figure 27: Evaluation of the importance to include for each grid point time series of the planetary boundary-layer height in the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas. The numbers provide the information how many percent of the participants selected one of the four pre-defined categories of answers.

For the group of consultants and project developers the corresponding numbers were 0%, 54%, 31% and 15%. Thus, there is a noticeable difference between the answers provided

by the whole group and by the subgroup of the consultants and project developers. Thus, researchers do still have to convince the consultants and project developers that to take into account information on the planetary boundary layer height might lead to an improved description of the wind profile and thus to a better wind resource assessment. On the other hand, the New European Wind Atlas is expected to provide anyhow information on the wind speed in different heights so that the inclusion of information on the planetary boundary-layer height may anyhow be superfluous.

Another parameter for which only a relatively low percentage (19%) of people answered that they do absolutely require time series data from that parameter was the inverse Obukhov length. 12% answered that they do not require time series data for this parameter at all (see Figure 28).

Figure 28: Evaluation of the importance to include for each grid point information time series of the inverse Obukhov length in the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas. The numbers provide the information how many percent of the participants selected one of the four pre-defined categories of answers.

The percentages obtained for the four different possibilities of answers were: 15%, 54%, 15% and 15%.

Exactly the same results as for the time series of the inverse Obukhov length were obtained for the time series of roughness length (see Figure 29).

Figure 29: Evaluation of the importance to include for each grid point time series of roughness length in the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas. The numbers provide the information how many percent of the participants selected one of the four pre-defined categories of answers.

To include information on the orography in the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas was considered to be absolutely required by a minority of 38% of all participants (see Figure 30).

Figure 30: Evaluation of the importance to include for each grid point information on underlying orography in the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas. The numbers provide the information how many percent of the participants selected one of the four pre-defined categories of answers.

Even for the group of consultants and project developers the people who said that they do absolutely require information on the orography were still in the minority with 46%. The percentages for the three remaining possibilities for answers were 31%, 8% and 15%.

Finally, the participants were asked whether they are interested in information on the land use that was applied for the generation of the meso-scale wind atlas. Also here, only a minority of 31% answered that they do absolutely require information on this parameter for their work (see Figure 31).

Figure 31: Evaluation of the importance to include for each grid point information on the underlying land use in the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas. The numbers provide the information how many percent of the participants selected one of the four pre-defined categories of answers.

The results obtained for the subgroup consisting of consultants and project developers were exactly the same as for the total group.

Summary:

The participants seem to prefer time series data compared to pure statistical information. According to the answers given by the participants the most important parameters seem to be time series of wind speed, wind direction and temperature. In order to allow for a calculation of the air density also time series of pressure might be required.

Question 15:

The participants mentioned the following additional parameters that should be included in the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas:

- “sunshine duration and surface temperature”,
- “extreme events”,
- “vorticity, wind gusts, insolation, precipitation”,
- “icing days”,
- “time series of shear, extreme wind”,
- “average Weibull parameters and frequency roses resulting from the time series”,
- “time series data of different heights”,
- “inflow angle”,
- “all parameters according to IEC 61400-1”.

Question 16:

When the participants were asked which were the most important parameters that should be included in the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas it turned out again that the stakeholders are actually more interested in time series data than in statistical data. The first five parameters that got the most nominations as most important information to be included in the New European Wind Atlas were all time series parameters: Time series of wind speed, of wind direction, of temperature, of turbulence intensity and of inverse Obukhov length (see Figure 32).

Figure 32: Number of nominations of different types of information by the participants of the questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a new European Wind Atlas as one of the five most important types of information to be provided in the New European Wind Atlas.

Question 17:

When the participants were asked whether, in case that the resources available to the project will allow for an increase of either the spatial resolution of the meso-scale or the spatial resolution of the micro-scale wind atlas compared to the specifications in the NEWA proposal (3 km and 30 m, respectively), the clear answer by the participants was that the resolution of the meso-scale wind atlas should be improved (see Figure 33).

Figure 33: Answers provided by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas to question 17 which asked whether the participant prefers an increase of the spatial resolution of the meso-scale wind atlas or an increase of the spatial resolution of the micro-scale wind atlas in case that there will

still be free computational and storage resources in the NEWA project after the specifications made in the NEWA proposal have been met.

Question 18:

The request to specify the ten most important vertical levels that should be included in the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas resulted in the specification of heights between 2 m, which is the meteorological standard measurement height, and 2000 m (see Figure 34). 33 of the 37 heights specified by the participants are within the interval between 2 m and 250 m.

Figure 34: Number of nominations of different vertical levels as being important to be included in the New European Wind Atlas by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas.

Question 19:

When asked which kind of statistics should be provided in the micro-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas, a majority of participants was answering that this kind of statistics is required only in case of annual statistics and monthly statistics. The interest in daily or hourly statistics was comparatively low (see Figure 37Figure 35 to Figure 39).

Figure 35: Evaluation of the importance to include annual statistics of certain parameters for each grid point in the micro-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas. The numbers provide the information how many percent of the participants selected one of the four pre-defined categories of answers.

Monthly statistics

Figure 36: Evaluation of the importance to include monthly statistics of certain parameters for each grid point in the micro-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas. The numbers provide the information how many percent of the participants selected one of the four pre-defined categories of answers.

Figure 37: Evaluation of the importance to include daily statistics of certain parameters for each grid point in the micro-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas. The numbers provide the information how many percent of the participants selected one of the four pre-defined categories of answers.

Figure 38: Evaluation of the importance to include hourly statistics of certain parameters for each grid point in the micro-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas. The numbers provide the information how many percent of the participants selected one of the four pre-defined categories of answers.

Hourly statistics per season

Figure 39: Evaluation of the importance to include hourly statistics of certain parameters for each season for each grid point in the micro-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a New European Wind Atlas. The numbers provide the information how many percent of the participants selected one of the four pre-defined categories of answers.

Question 20:

Asked for the information that should be included in the micro-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas the participants gave the following answers:

- "Annual wind rose (frequency, energy), annual average wind speed and energy density, monthly statistics of Monin-Obukhov length (frequency of occurrence of unstable/neutral/stable situations in percent)",
- "Wind speed by sector and month, air density by sector and month, turbulence by sector and month",
- "Weibull parameters, frequency distributions, turbulence intensity, air density or temperature",
- "Wind speed, wind direction, temperature".

Question 21:

Asked for the level of uncertainty of the data that would still be acceptable, the different participants provided very different answers. The answers obtained were the following:

- "Within 1.0 m/s",
- "5%",
- "TP wind vision: 3% But let's make it 3% wind speed rather than 3% energy - please note that in TP Wind nobody spoke about direction! This is not to be neglected! The modeled wind direction should have an accuracy of 10 degree. It is crucial for layouts to have the direction (together with speed) right!",
- "Uncertainties should be not much bigger than those coming up with conventional methods (reference wind farms + wind index or wind measurement + long term source)",
- "1% e.g. wind 0.05 m/s",

- “15-20%”,
- “0.5 m/s”,
- “plus minus 0.25m/s (but how do you plan to verify that?)”,
- “±0.1 m/s (pretty hard though)”,
- “The uncertainty on wind speed for on-site measurement is between 2% (short term) and 5% (long term). Around 5% uncertainty on wind speed would already be very useful.”

Question 22:

Only about half of all participants gave an answer to the question which type of uncertainty information they expect to obtain from the New European Wind Atlas. Those answers that were obtained did not reveal a clear picture. About half of the answers supported the idea to derive uncertainty information from an ensemble approach, while the other half wanted to have information on how much the conditions differ over a single grid box of the meso-scale grid.

Question 23:

About ¾ of the participants would like to have information on the predictability of wind resources included in the New European Wind Atlas (see Figure 40). The vast majority of these people are interested in how well the long-term wind resources can be predicted at a certain site. The short-term predictability is still of minor interest.

Figure 40: Answers provided by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders’ expectations to a New European Wind Atlas to question 23 in which the interest of the participant in information on the predictability of wind on different time-scales was inquired. Note: Multiple answers to this question were possible.

Question 24:

50% of the participants considered information on the frequency of icing events as important to be included in the New European Wind Atlas. 31% said information on the frequency of icing events is not required, while 19% did not give an answer.

Question 25:

Among the extreme parameters offered to the participants only the extreme wind speed was considered as being absolutely required by a vast majority of the participants (77%). 15% answered that information on extreme wind speeds would be a nice to have, 4%

answered that they do not need such type of information and 4 % did not submit their evaluation.

For the extreme wind speed gradients in time the numbers obtained were 15%, 77 %, 4% and 4%.

For the extreme vertical shear the numbers obtained were 35%, 58%, 4% and 4%.

And, finally, the numbers obtained for the extreme values of turbulence intensity were 42%, 50%, 4% and 4%.

Question 26:

The vast majority of participants suggested to provide extreme values for a recurrence period of 50 years.

It was suggested to provide information on extremes for all parameters mentioned in IEC 61400-1 (IEC 2005). A couple of participants asked also for information on the frequency of thunderstorms or even the lightning activity.

Question 27:

Only 38% of the participants answered that they expect that the New European Wind Atlas will provide information on wave parameters, while 46% answered that they do not expect to get such information. 15% did not provide an answer. Those participants who wanted to have information on wave parameters, suggested to provide those parameters that are mentioned in IEC 61400-3 (IEC 2009).

Question 28:

The favorite ways to get access to the information included in the New European Wind Atlas are downloadable data files or a direct access to a data base. According to the answers obtained in the questionnaire there is no need to develop a special software for the New European Wind Atlas as such a solution would anyhow not be the stakeholders' favorite way of getting access to the New European Wind Atlas (see Figure 41).

Figure 41: Answers given by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a new European Wind Atlas to question 28 of the questionnaire in which the participants were asked what would be their favorite way to get access to the New European Wind Atlas. Note that the percentages do not sum up to 100% as it was allowed to specify several answers.

Question 29:

Besides their favorite ways of access the stakeholders use online maps if those were offered, as can be seen in Figure 42 where the results to the question which ways of access to the New European Wind Atlas would actually be utilized, are illustrated.

Figure 42: Answers given by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a new European Wind Atlas to question 29 of the questionnaire in which the participants were asked which ways of access to

the data of the New European Wind Atlas. what would be their favorite way to get access to the New European Wind Atlas. Note that the percentages do not sum up to 100% as it was allowed to specify several answers.

Question 30:

According to the results presented in Figure 43 the favorite data format in which the data of the New European Wind Atlas should be provided is a simple CSV data format. In case that the data were provided in a GIS Format it should be a GIS format that can be processed by free GIS software.

Figure 43: Answers given by the participants of the online questionnaire on stakeholders' expectations to a new European Wind Atlas to question 30 of the questionnaire in which the participants were asked in which format data of the New European Wind Atlas should be provided. Note that the percentages do not sum up to 100% as it was allowed to specify several answers.

Question 31:

It was difficult for the participants to specify the value of the New European Wind Atlas. Most of the participants answered that they cannot specify the value. Others tried to estimate how much they would be willing to pay per year to get access to the data, but the numbers obtained differed a lot. The lowest number mentioned was 100 €/year the largest number mentioned was 50000 €. For the largest number given it was not indicated whether this would be really an annual fee or a single payment. Several participants mentioned that they expect that there will be a free access to the New European Wind Atlas as it is a product of a project paid by the tax payers.

Question 32:

Some participants would be interested in an extension of the New European Wind Atlas to the Balkan states. Others answered that they would be interested if the area could be extended to Northern Africa. Some participants expected that the New European Wind Atlas will cover the whole of Europe.

Question 33:

With the last question the participants obtained the opportunity to summarize their expectations to a New European Wind Atlas. In the following selected answers given by the participants are summarized:

- One participant expected the New European Wind Atlas to provide information on the spatial variation of wind resources in difficult terrain such as near-coastal areas.
- There was the expectation expressed that the New European Wind Atlas can serve as a reference as it will offer the same quality of data for a huge part of Europe.
- One participant mentioned that depending on the magnitude of the accuracy of the data in the New European Wind Atlas the participant's organization would use the New European Wind Atlas for different purposes. If the accuracy of the data is relatively low and only average wind statistics and wind roses are offered, the data will be used for an estimation of the local wind regime for site prospecting, i.e. before a met mast is actually installed. If the accuracy is moderate, the data will be used for data completion or long-term extrapolation of on-site measurement. The stability time series will be used as input for the micro-scale calculations. If indeed the TP Wind vision of an accuracy of 3% were reached, the New European Wind Atlas could replace met masts and the data contained in it could be used to do a full energy yield assessment.
- One participant expressed the hope that the New European Wind Atlas will play a key role in the development of future wind models and thus will contribute to improve the exploitation of wind resources.
- Another participant mentioned that especially information on the uncertainties is important. Moreover, the verification process should be well documented and also the model chain that will be developed within the NEWA project should be well documented so that it can easily be applied also by the users of the New European Wind Atlas.
- The next participant wrote that it is important that the New European Wind Atlas will not only contain data. There were already other wind atlases that offer a lot of parameters, but there were no hints how this data could be used to improve the results of the work of a consultant or project developer. So to have more information was good, but only if the stakeholders knew how to make use of this data. This implies that this participant would like to be provided with well-documented guidelines how the data in the New European Wind Atlas should be used in order to reach an improved quality of wind resource assessments.
- One participant mentioned that the sources of all the data in the New European Wind Atlas should be well documented.

- Another participant wrote that he or she expects that it is of importance that the New European Wind Atlas will be easy to use and easy to access.
- The next participant pointed out that the data of the New European Wind Atlas should be consistent in space and time and that information on the uncertainties should be provided. Moreover, for this participant it was important that the New European Wind Atlas will provide forcing data for micro-scale models for a detailed micro-siting.
- Another participant wrote that he or she expects to obtain reliable wind information on the European scale from a New European Wind Atlas.
- A high spatial and temporal resolution of the data and the provision of time-series data were the expectation of the next participant.
- One participant mentioned that the data base for the offshore regions would be especially important.

3. Preliminary conclusions for the design of the New European Wind Atlas

The results obtained from the analysis of the answers given to the questions in the questionnaire reveal that there is quite some interest in the New European Wind Atlas.

The three columns of the modelling part of the New European Wind Atlas, a meso-scale wind atlas, a micro-scale wind atlas and a methodology with which the meso-scale data can be further downscaled to the micro-scale are generally accepted by the stakeholders.

Including also data from measurement campaigns in the data base as suggested in the NEWA proposal meets the expectation of the users to allow at least for a pointwise validation of the data in the New European Wind Atlas. Moreover, it will allow for a validation in case that a user intends to use his own downscaling approach for the transfer from the meso- to the micro-scale or in case that in future further developed meso-scale models will become available and the user wants to check the benefit of these developments with regard to wind resource assessment in combination with the downscaling technique from meso- to micro-scale to be developed in the framework of the NEWA project.

Based on the answers given to the online questionnaire it seems as if the stakeholders consider the development of a verified methodology with which meso-scale data can be used as input for further calculations with a micro-scale model for a specific site as most important. The users would like to have clear guidelines how the downscaling can be done. Moreover, they would like to get clear information on the uncertainties that are connected with all data and methodologies that are provided by the New European Wind Atlas.

The second largest interest of the stakeholders seems to be the meso-scale wind atlas. The stakeholders wish that the way how the meso-scale wind atlas will be derived will be well-documented. The data of this wind-atlas should be applicable as input data for the further downscaling with a micro-scale model. The users are especially interested in being provided with time-series data from the meso-scale wind atlas. If time series of a parameter are provided in the meso-scale wind atlas it should be made clear how the application of this parameter in the process of further downscaling to the micro-scale helps to improve the results. To provide a lot of data alone is not in the interest of the stakeholders, they need guidance what the data is actually good for.

Compared with the specifications in the NEWA proposal the stakeholders ask for a considerably increased spatial resolution as well as a considerably increased extension of the time period that is covered by the New European Wind Atlas. While in the NEWA proposal it was specified that the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas should have a spatial resolution of at least 3 km, the stakeholders actually would like to have a spatial resolution of the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas of about 1 km. The period that should be covered by the meso-scale wind atlas was expected to be at least 10 years in the NEWA proposal. According to the answers given by the stakeholders

in the questionnaire the wind atlas should actually cover a time period of 25 years to meet the needs of the stakeholders. The envisaged temporal resolution of 10 minutes is in agreement with the expectations of the users. As the computational and storage resources available to the project will be limited it is not clear whether the expectations of the users concerning the length of the wind atlas period and the spatial resolution of the meso-scale wind atlas can actually be fully met. It is however intended to accommodate as much as possible to the expectations of the stakeholders.

Concerning the parameters that should be provided in the meso-scale part of the New European Wind Atlas, no final decision can already be reported in this document. The problem is that the final output list depends on the methodology that is still to be developed to further downscale the meso-scale data to the micro-scale. Here only a preliminary recommendation can be given that is based on the specifications made by the participants of the questionnaire.

Meeting the expectations of the stakeholders and the specifications in the IEC standards (IEC 2005) time series data should be provided for the following parameters:

- horizontal wind speed,
- wind direction,
- turbulence intensity,
- air temperature,
- pressure,
- inclination of the flow,
- relative humidity,
- inverse Obukhov length.

For each of these parameters it should be specified what actually the benefit of a consideration of these parameters in a wind resource assessment is. This could e.g. be done by including examples of wind resource assessment studies in the data base of the New European Wind Atlas. The New European Wind Atlas should include all necessary information that would allow the end user to repeat the calculations. In case that no benefit of using certain parameters can be shown in exemplary studies there will be no need to include the parameters in the final data base.

Moreover, for the meso-scale wind atlas it should be documented which orography data and which land use information has been used for the calculation of the meso-scale wind atlas.

Although the interest in such data is only moderate, the meso-scale wind atlas should provide also some statistics, e.g. information on the wind speed distributions per direction sector (where the maximum width of a direction sector should not exceed 10° , as micro-siting sites for wind farms will certainly be one of the main applications for the New European Wind Atlas and the efficiency of wind farms can be strongly dependent on the wind direction (Porté-Agel, 2013)). The statistics should be provided based on the whole time series, only on parts of the time series from a certain month of the year and on parts of the time series from a certain hour of the day. The distributions should not exclusively

be described by the Weibull parameters but also as raw distributions due to the drastically increased amount of storage available today compared to roughly thirty years ago when the European Wind Atlas (Troen and Petersen, 1989) has been prepared by DTU. Moreover, information on the mean values, minima, maxima and standard deviations should be provided for those parameters for which also time series data is provided. Additionally, information on the frequency of situations with stable, neutral and unstable stratifications at each grid point of the meso-scale atlas should be provided for each month of the year. The statistical data will provide data that is easily accessible for mapping and will therefore allow for a first rough comparison of wind conditions at several sites.

Finally, also the regional wind climate, i.e. some kind of generalized wind climate, should be derived from the meso-scale data. For the derivation of the generalized wind climate a methodology developed for the European Wind Atlas (Troen and Petersen, 1989) can be applied. The application for this method to data from a numerical model is documented e.g. for the work concerning the generation of a wind atlas for Egypt (Mortensen et al., 2006)

Concerning the height levels for which data should be provided the following is suggested based on the answers of the participants and an analysis of the dimensions of today commercially available wind turbines. For an easy comparison with the data of meteorological stations data should be provided at 2 m and 10 m height. 2 m is the WMO's standard height for measurements of temperature, humidity and pressure, while 10 m is the WMO's standard height for the measurement of wind direction and wind speed. In addition there should be eleven vertical levels from 50 to 250 m with increments of 20 m to allow for a full coverage of the rotor layers of today available wind turbines.

The interest in a pre-calculated statistical micro-scale wind atlas is comparatively low. Some stakeholders mentioned that they do not use statistical data any longer, but that nowadays they are using exclusively time series data. The resolution of 30 m suggested in the NEWA proposal was accepted by the participants of the questionnaire.

The following outputs should be provided in the pre-calculated micro-scale wind atlas. It should provide wind speed distributions per direction sector. The width of the direction sector should not be larger than 10° . The distributions should be provided based on different reference periods: the whole time series, only parts of the time series from a certain month of the year and only parts of the time series from a certain hour of the day. Again information on the distributions should be provided in the form of Weibull parameters as well as by giving the raw data. Moreover, the micro-scale wind atlas should provide information on the mean air density, the mean pressure, the mean temperature and if possible also the mean power density. Finally, information on the underlying orography as well as the underlying land use should be given.

Concerning the accuracy it should be headed for an accuracy of 3% (concerning the wind speed). However, it has to be taken into account that the standard accuracy of long-term

wind speed measurements is in the range of 5%. Thus, to prove that an accuracy of 3% has been reached in the end will be difficult.

In order to estimate the uncertainty of the data of the meso-scale wind atlas two approaches should be followed in the framework of the NEWA project. It should be tried to set up an ensemble of meso-scale downscaling calculations, but it should also be tried to provide information on how much the data varies within a grid box of the meso-scale model. One suggestion to get an estimate for this variation might be an approach similar to one from the Global Wind Atlas project (documented on <http://globalwindatlas.com/datasets.html>). Based on the results of the micro-scale wind atlas the variability of wind resources over one grid box of the meso-scale model could be estimated via the method of aggregated top-quartile bottom-quartile mean wind speed differences.

As one result of the questionnaire it turned out that the stakeholders are very much interested in getting information on extreme events. The interest is especially high in the group of consultants and project developers. Therefore, some resources should be spent on the derivation of information on extreme events within the project. The stakeholders asked for extreme values for recurrence periods of 10, 20 and 50 years. In the IEC standard information on extreme events for recurrence periods of 1 and 50 years are required. To meet both requirements we suggest to provide information for recurrence periods of 1, 10, 20 and 50 years. In accordance with standards set by the IEC the New European Wind Atlas should provide at least information on extreme values for the following parameters: wind speed, turbulence intensity, vertical shear, wind direction change with time, wind direction change with height and temperature. Information on the frequency of thunderstorms could also be derived from the mesoscale simulations, while it will be difficult to meet the request of some stakeholders to provide also information on the lightning activity. In the NEWA proposal it was actually indicated that the models for the derivation of the extreme values will also become part of the New European Wind Atlas data base.

Half of the participants of the questionnaire asked to provide information on the frequency of icing events. Therefore, it is suggested to invest some work in the derivation of information on the frequency of icing events from the planned meso-scale simulations. For the derivation of information on the frequency of icing events some postprocessing of the meso-scale data will be necessary. The corresponding code should also become part of the data base of the New European Wind Atlas so that users of this data base will be able to apply it to other meso-scale time series as well.

On the other hand, only about 1/3 of the participants expect information on wave parameters to be included in the New European Wind Atlas. Therefore, work on the derivation of corresponding parameters should only be given a comparatively low priority.

Several participants mentioned that one aspect that makes a wind atlas attractive for them is an easy access to the data base. The participants would like to be able to download certain data files and they would prefer to get the data provided in a simple

format such as a CSV data format. Easy mapping of the wind atlas data is also a wish of the stakeholders. Actually, corresponding work has already been foreseen in the NEWA proposal.

The value that the New European Wind Atlas will have to them could not easily be estimated by the participants of the wind atlas. The participants are however interested in an extension of the wind atlas to further areas. This could be done in a follow-up project. If this follow-up project is privately funded it might mean some possibility for a commercial add-on to the publicly funded wind atlas. The highest priority according to the stakeholders might have an extension to the remaining countries of Europe followed by an extension to Northern Africa.

Finally, some comments on the concept of the work done in task 4.1 should be made. With hindsight it might have been better to come to a more detailed and more clear idea for the contents of the New European Wind Atlas within the project consortium before asking the stakeholders for their opinion concerning the developed ideas. The strategy actually chosen, asking the stakeholders at first and then developing a detailed idea about the contents of the New European Wind Atlas, might have had the disadvantage that the participants of the questionnaire had no clear idea about the product that should be developed in the New European Wind Atlas and that they had to answer a lot of rather widely composed questions. This might have increased the number of people that started to answer the questions in the questionnaire but finally gave up to reply to the questions after a certain time. In the end only a rather low number of replies to the questionnaire have been obtained. This implies the risk that the answers given by the participants are not fully representative for the whole of the community of potential users of the New European Wind Atlas. In the weeks and months after the analysis of the answers to the online questionnaire and the preparation of a first draft of this deliverable the preliminary results obtained were further discussed with the project partners as well as with the stakeholders. By this it should e.g. be made sure that also the requirements of the micro-scale modelers concerning meso-scale data are properly taken into account in the final NEWA data base.

4. Evaluation of the expectations of the end users within the project consortium

Besides during the NEWA workshop in Copenhagen mentioned above and besides the communication to the project participants by e-mail, the results of the questionnaire on the expectations of the end users concerning the New European Wind Atlas have also been presented to the project consortium during the NEWA project meeting in Perdigao on May 11th, 2016.

During this meeting the findings of the questionnaire were questioned again.

The most critical point mentioned by the participants in the Perdigao workshop was the limited amount of disk space that will be available to host the NEWA data base and that it is dubious, whether it will be possible to host all the data that has been considered to be important by the stakeholders who answered to the questionnaire.

As a conclusion, it was decided that a priority list of output parameters should be made by the project participants. In case that it turned out that the storage available for hosting of the data base is indeed too small, those parameters that have been given a low priority would not become part of the NEWA data base.

In order to inquire the priorities for the different parameters earlier suggested to be contained in the NEWA data base, a new survey using the online tool consider.it has been carried out. Again, the participation in that survey was rather moderate with fifteen people taking part in it.

However, as an important input also suggestions for further output parameters that might be required for a coupling between meso- and micro-scale models could be obtained, as actually people working on the meso-to-micro-scale-coupling took part in the survey.

Note that during the meeting in Perdigao also additional parameters had been suggested. These were also included in the consider.it survey.

Table 4.1 provides detailed information on the priorities assigned to the different parameters. In this table the output parameters are actually ordered by their assigned priority.

Table 4.1: Priorities given by participants in the second survey (consider.it-survey) on wind atlas output parameters to different parameters suggested to be included in the data base of the New European Wind Atlas

Parameter	Priority given by participants in consider.it-survey (scale from -1 to 1)
Horizontal wind speed	+1.00
Wind direction	+0.88

Air temperature	+0.77
Obukhov length	+0.64
Geostrophic wind at the surface	+0.64
Pressure	+0.55
Planetary boundary layer height	+0.53
Friction velocity	+0.46
Turbulence intensity	+0.38
Relative humidity	+0.21
Roughness length	+0.18
Sea surface temperature	+0.16
Vertical wind speed	-0.02
Air density	-0.03
Geostrophic wind at velocity levels	-0.36
Wind shear	-0.50

One suggestion during the project meeting in Perdigao was to provide certain parameters only on certain height levels in order to reduce the size of the final NEWA data base. However, the level of acceptance of such a proposal among the participants in the survey was rather low with a number of -0.63 for air temperature and -0.03 for relative humidity. On the other hand a number of 0.33 for pressure indicates that a majority of participants would agree with the provision of pressure at a single height level only.

As a conclusion one can state that among the project partners it seems to be acceptable not to provide information on vertical wind speed, air density (which can instead be computed from pressure, air density and relative humidity), geostrophic wind at all height levels and wind shear (which can be derived from wind speed at different height levels instead) in the final NEWA data base. Limiting the pressure to one height level only might be an option to further reduce the amount of data stored in the NEWA data base.

Another possibility to limit the amount of data in the NEWA data base are to restrict the output of friction velocity to offshore regions only. Information on the roughness height

over the land is not required with a resolution of 10 minutes but information on seasonal changes of the roughness length should be provided in the NEWA data base.

On the other hand, while in the second survey it was only asked to provide an information on the importance of the provision of the sea surface temperature, further discussions showed that also an information on the surface temperature will be required by the micro-scale modelers at land points.

The next possibility to limit the size of the NEWA data base if this is absolutely required is to reduce the number of output levels. Therefore, the project participants have also been asked to assign priorities to the different height levels that had earlier been suggested as output levels of the New European Wind Atlas.

Table 4.2 summarizes the priorities assigned by the survey participants to the different output levels that had earlier been suggested.

Table 4.2: Priorities given by participants in the second survey (consider.it-survey) on wind atlas output parameters to different output levels suggested to be included in the data base of the New European Wind Atlas

Height level	Priority given by participants in consider.it-survey (scale from -1 to 1)
100 m	+0.94
200 m	+0.77
50 m	+0.69
150 m	+0.64
75 m	+0.53
2 / 10 m	+0.18

None of the output levels earlier specified was considered to be ubiquitous by a majority of the participants. However, the level of acceptance to include also near-surface heights of 2 m and 10 m in the New European Wind Atlas was much lower than the level of acceptance for all other levels. If there is a need to reduce the size of the NEWA data base the levels closest to the surface might therefore be the first levels that should be skipped. It is nevertheless worth mentioning that most measurements are available at height of 2 m and 10 m. Thus, not adding these height levels might lead to considerably smaller possibilities to compare the New European Wind Atlas with measurements. This might make the New European Wind Atlas less attractive for end users, as has been mentioned in answers to the first questionnaire and also in interviews by consultants.

The statement that an output level of 500 m is sufficient to provide an information on the wind resource for high-altitude wind energy converter systems has found more acceptance than refusal among the participants of the second questionnaire. Thus, information also on that level should be provided in the New European Wind Atlas.

The next critical question expressed during the project meeting in Perdigao concerning the results of the stakeholder questionnaire was: Does it make sense from a scientific point of view to increase the resolution of the wind and stability atlas to more than 3 km?

To answer this question a literature review has been carried out. However, no publication could be found in which it had actually be shown that using a resolution better than 3 km would generally result in more accurate estimates of the wind resources at a certain site.

The conclusion here was that initially the originally intended resolution of 3 km should be kept. However, sensitivity studies will be carried out in the further course of the project in order to evaluate whether using a higher spatial resolution results in an improved accuracy of the estimate of the wind resources.

The third critical question was whether it is really necessary to provide time series that cover a period of 25 years.

Some people in the audience expressed their opinion that it is not required to deliver time series from a mesoscale model for 25 years. Different arguments were mentioned. One argument was that a short time period of several years together with reanalysis data might be sufficient to allow for the construction of a time series of 25 years based on a combined dynamical and statistical downscaling approach (MCP or analog ensemble methods). Results of applications of the analog ensemble method let one suggest that it might indeed be possible to yield similarly accurate results with this method compared to a pure dynamical downscaling but with considerably less computational efforts (Zhang et al., 2015). Therefore, this method will be checked in the framework of the New European Wind Atlas project as well. If it turns out that the results presented in literature so far, can be reproduced, this might allow for indeed reducing the number of output years stored in the New European Wind Atlas. However, this would also mean that a methodology should be provided in the New European Wind Atlas that describes how the analog ensemble can be derived including the derivation of weighting factors of certain predictors.

Another suggestion was to provide only a wind atlas with a coarser resolution of 9 km for the period of 25 years, while providing the wind atlas with a resolution of 3 km for 10 years only. This would save a lot of storage capacity. This suggestion found with a number of 0.72 a rather high level of agreement among project participants in the second internal survey on the data base of the New European Wind Atlas. Therefore, this suggestion should further be studied.

Another critical point mentioned concerning the length of the time series was that the land use can change dramatically over a period of 25 years. Thus, it is questionable whether the results derived for the 25 years will still be valid for future. Thus, it might be important to offer also information that is free of the surface influence. Thus, it might be

recommended to provide also time series of a kind of generalized wind as the generalized wind in the current European Wind Atlas that is free of surface influences. Note however that the argument of a changing surface is not valid for the complete offshore regions included in the New European Wind Atlas. Of course the wind conditions there might also be influenced by changes in the roughness conditions in surrounding land areas, but further away from the coastline the influence of the surrounding land area should be able to be considered as negligible.

From a climatological point of view it has to be stated once again that a time series with a length of only 10 years will be too short to provide an adequate estimate of the wind resources that can be expected over 20 years, which is the typical time of operation of a wind farm and therefore also used in yield estimates for new wind farms.

The fourth critical question was whether it makes sense to provide time series with a resolution of 10 minutes if the spatial resolution is only 3 km. Actually, it is worth checking whether time series with a temporal resolution of 10 minutes lead to a dramatically improved accuracy of wind resource estimates compared to time series with a resolution of only one hour. In case that a negligible difference between the results for wind resource assessments using the two different temporal resolutions is obtained, providing data with a temporal resolution of 10 minutes is considered to be sufficient.

The fifth critical question was whether the New European Wind Atlas should also contain data with a low quality or whether data with low quality should be removed completely from the data base. The majority of participants taking part in the second survey on the output parameters of the New European Wind Atlas expressed their opinion that also low quality data should be contained. However, it has to be made sure that data with low quality is clearly flagged and end users will be warned to use that data.

During the project meeting in Perdigao it arose also a discussion on generating a second data base. Some project partners suggested that there should be a special data base that hosts all data that would be required by the developers of the mesoscale to microscale coupling approach. The contents of that data base do not necessarily need to be in agreement with the finally publicly accessible NEWA data base.

Important decisions were taken concerning the list of extreme values that will be provided in the New European Wind Atlas. As it was found that there is not enough expertise in the project consortium to provide adequate information on the frequency of thunderstorms / lightning as well as for deriving accurate information on wave parameters it was decided not to include corresponding information in the final data base of the New European Wind Atlas. On the other hand it was found that several project partners have considerable experience in the estimation of icing risks for wind turbines. Therefore, in a task lead by DTU and Weathertech it will be attempted to derive information on the risk of icing of wind turbines for inclusion in the final data base of the New European Wind Atlas.

Concerning the mesoscale wind atlas it has finally to be mentioned that in addition it might be necessary to provide further information on the bottom boundary conditions for the

microscale modelling such as the near-surface heat flux. Alternatively, this parameter could however also be derived from the Obukhov length and friction velocity.

Prior to the project meeting in Perdigao some more detailed specifications of the microscale wind atlas have been achieved. Wind speed distributions should be provided per wind direction sector and the suggested width of a wind direction sector should be 7.5° . The information should be provided for the whole year, but also for single months. Moreover, information on the annual and monthly average wind speed as well as on energy density will be provided. The frequency of occurrence of unstable / neutral / stable situations will be provided on an annual and on a monthly basis. Information on the mean air density will be provided by wind direction sector on an annual and monthly basis. The same will be valid for the turbulence intensity. Moreover, information on the terrain height and the roughness length will be provided in the microscale wind atlas. An important point is that the microscale part of the New European Wind Atlas should be compatible with the Global Wind Atlas that has recently been created by DTU for the International Renewable Energy Agency. Thus, the wind atlas should indeed provide information on the roughness for each wind direction sector, the roughness speed up, the orographic speed up and the percentage of steep terrain within a certain upstream distance from the grid point.

A critical point in the definition of the output parameters of the New European Wind Atlas is that the disk space that is available to host the NEWA data base is limited. About 300 TB will be available to host the NEWA data base. According to the suggestions made above by far the largest share of the NEWA data base will be made up by time series data from mesoscale simulations. In the following a rough estimate for the size of the mesoscale time series data will be provided. In the ClusterDesign project (for detailed information on the project see <https://www.cluster-design.eu>) a wind and stability atlas covering the Southern North Sea has been generated. The wind and stability atlas provided information for a number of 26992 grid points. The spatial resolution was 2 km. There were five parameters that were provided on five output levels and there were three output parameters that were provided on only one level. The time period covered by the wind and stability atlas of the ClusterDesign project comprised the twenty years between 1993 and 2012 and the temporal resolution of the time series contained in this data set were 10 minutes. The total size of the wind and stability atlas in the NEWA project was 1 TB.

Let us now assume a spatial resolution of the New European Wind Atlas of 3 km, a covered period of 25 years with a temporal resolution of ten minutes. The size of the European landmass is $10.532.000 \text{ km}^2$, the size of the Baltic Sea is 412.500 km^2 , the size of the North Sea is 750.000 km^2 . Assuming another $2.000.000 \text{ km}^2$ of near-coastal offshore regions that should be covered by the New European Wind Atlas, a rough estimate for the total size of area covered by the New European Wind Atlas will be $13.750.000 \text{ km}^2$. According to the specifications above about six parameters will be output at eight output levels, while another six parameters will only be output at a single height level. Thus, based on the size of the wind and stability atlas of the ClusterDesign project the estimate for the size of such a kind of data set would be about 137 TB, which would fit well within the limit defined by half of the total size of the NEWA data base. Reducing the temporal resolution

from ten minutes to one hour would result in a reduction of the size of the wind atlas to about 23 TB.

5. Final proposal for the list of output parameters

The findings from the second survey were presented to the members of the project consortium on a workshop in Barcelona that took place from September 21st to September 23rd, 2016. In the following lines the final proposal for wind atlas output parameters that has been deduced from the discussions in Barcelona will be presented.

5.1 Mesoscale wind atlas

Temporal resolution of the data in the mesoscale wind atlas

The preliminary suggestion for the temporal resolution of the time series contained in the mesoscale wind atlas is that this resolution should be 1 h. It is intended to support this decision by comparing the statistics obtained from mesoscale time series with a resolution of 1 h with those obtained from mesoscale time series with a resolution of 10 minutes. A preliminary investigation at ForWind (Wurps, 2016) showed that the differences in the bias and root-mean square errors of wind speed and turbulent kinetic energy at the FINO1 met mast are negligible between the mesoscale time series with a resolution of 10 minutes and 1 h. The results of Wurps (2016) were based on a measured and simulated time series with a length of one year.

In order to get reliable estimates of long-term wind resources at a site, it is more important to extend the period covered by the wind atlas than in to provide data with a temporal resolution better than 1 h.

Period covered by the mesoscale wind atlas

The mesoscale wind atlas will cover a period of 30 years in order to cover a full climatological period. The land surface information will be kept constant during the 30 years of simulation.

Spatial resolution of the data in the mesoscale wind atlas

The preliminary suggestion for the spatial resolution of the mesoscale data in the New European Wind Atlas is 3 km. In case that not enough computational resources are available to do a dynamical downscaling for the whole of Europe with a spatial resolution of 3 km for a period of 30 years, a hybrid approach will be followed: data from a period of only 10 years will then be provided with a spatial resolution of 3 km, while in addition 30 years of data will be provided with a spatial resolution of 9 km. This will still allow the further downscaling of the 9 km resolution data by statistical means using the data from the overlap period of the time series with a resolution of 9 and 3 km.

Height levels for which data is provided in the mesoscale wind atlas

Certain parameters of the wind atlas will be provided at several height levels. These height levels are the WMO standard height levels of 2 m (thermodynamic parameters) and 10 m (wind) as well as the upper height levels of 50 m, 75 m, 100 m, 150 m, 200 m, 250 m and 500 m above ground level. Thus, a number of output parameters will be available at eight heights. On the other hand there is also a number of parameters that will only be provided as single time series. Examples are time series of bottom boundary conditions or parameters describing properties of certain parts of the atmospheric boundary layer.

Time series parameters in the mesoscale wind atlas

Parameters that will be provided at all of the eight height levels specified above are

- horizontal wind speed,
- wind direction,
- air temperature,
- air pressure,
- turbulence intensity and
- relative humidity.

Parameters that will only be provided as a single time series are

- inverse Obukhov length,
- geostrophic wind,
- boundary-layer height,
- friction velocity,
- roughness length,
- sea / near-surface temperature.

Quality of data in the mesoscale wind atlas

In order to point out that the data from the mesoscale model is always spatially averaged data and that therefore comparisons with data from measurements which are usually done over much smaller measurement volumes need to be handled with care, the names of the time series parameters in the mesoscale wind atlas should include the subscript 'meso'. Moreover, if one of the suggested parameters cannot be provided as high-quality data it is suggested not to include data for that parameter in the wind atlas.

Statistical part of the mesoscale wind atlas

Besides the time series data the mesoscale wind atlas should also provide some statistical information. The statistical information will be provided on a grid with a grid spacing of 3 km. The statistics include wind speed distributions as well as information on wind power density, air density, roughness length and orography information for wind

direction sectors with a width of 15. The wind speed distributions will be provided as raw data as well as derived Weibull parameters. The temporal changing statistics will be provided for the full year, every month of a year as well as for every hour of a day. The statistical part of the mesoscale wind atlas will also provide mean values, minima and maxima of the time series parameters. Moreover, it will provide information on the frequency of occurrence of stable, neutral and unstable stratification.

5.2 Microscale wind atlas

The microscale wind atlas will be a purely statistical data set. It will provide information on wind energy related parameters with a spatial resolution of 30 m. The output parameters will be at least those of the DTU Global Wind Atlas (<http://www.globalwindatlas.com>). This means that for wind direction sectors of 15° the microscale wind atlas will provide information on the surface roughness, the roughness speed up / orographic speed up at a certain height, the ruggedness index, wind speed and power density. Aggregated wind and power density data might provide an idea on the spatial variability of wind resources in a certain area. Depending on the capabilities of the model that will be used to derive the microscale wind atlas it shall be attempted to provide as many of those parameters for which statistical information is provided in the mesoscale wind atlas also in the microscale wind atlas. The reference periods for the microscale wind atlas will be at least a full year as well as the single months of a year.

5.3 Additional parameters

An approach how to assign a certain icing class to each grid point of the mesoscale wind atlas will be suggested in the further course of the project by Weathertech. The final decision which extreme values will become part of the New European Wind Atlas will be taken in Task 4.2 of the NEWA project.

5.4 Uncertainty information

The main parameters in the New European Wind Atlas will be provided together with an uncertainty information. The exact approach will be specified as part of Task 4.4 .

Annex: Proposal for Wind Atlas Output Parameters – overview

Mesoscale wind atlas

- **Time series (1-h data)**
 - 3 km resolution
 - 30 years (option: hybrid approach -> 10 years with 3 km, remaining period with 9 km)
 - Time series parameters:
(*at all height levels*) horizontal wind speed, wind direction, air temperature, air pressure, turbulence intensity*, relative humidity
(*only one time series*) inverse Obukhov length, geostrophic wind, boundary-layer height, friction velocity, roughness length, sea / near-surface temperature
- *only data of 'high quality', chose name of parameter in database with care
- Height levels: 2 / 10 m, 50 m, 75 m, 100 m, 150 m, 200 m, 250 m, 500 m (# 8)
 - **Statistics:** wind speed distributions for 15° wind direction sectors (-> raw data and Weibull distributions) + wind power density, air density, roughness length, orography information;
different reference periods (year, month, hour of day);
mean values, min, max, std. dev. Of time series parameters;
frequency of stable / neutral / unstable stratification

Microscale wind atlas

- **Purely statistical**
- Same output parameters as above
- 30 m resolution
- Output parameters (same as DTU Global Wind Atlas):
Roughness per direction sector, roughness speed up / orographic speed up per sector at certain height, ruggedness index, wind speed and power density, aggregated wind and power density data
- Wind speed distribution per wind direction sector -> 15° sector width

- Reference periods: year, month

Additional parameters

- Icing class – approach suggested by WeatherTech
- Extreme values – to be detailed as part of Task 4.2

Uncertainty information

- (Main) parameters will be provided together with uncertainty information – exact approach to be specified as part of Task 4.4

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